

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 13.14/2024

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 7, 31 Июль

Methodology for applying innovative and pedagogical technologies in the development of creativity abilities of students through the national dance tool

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Abstract: This article will talk about the main features of the musical culture of Uzbekistan and Uzbek dance art. Opinions and information about the process of historical development of musical art, musical life, Uzbek national dance, how to use innovative technologies in order to develop interests in this art in students are described. Dance is considered a type of art, in which movements, compositions are made up of a certain rhythm and tempo, performed through emotional impressions that arise on the basis of the labor process of mankind and changes in domestic life. Of course, there are directions in which the dance art of each people, dance traditions, style of performance, visual means are performed in the direction of melody and music. Today, there is a growing need for students to spend their extracurricular time meaningfully. The need lies in improving the methods of performance skills in the development of creativity, the continuity of the theory and practice of performance skills and the need to know the principles of didactics, such as science, systemicity, sequence and consistency, enriching them with unbiased conclusions. Taking into account the important features of didactics, as well as other subjects, in the educational process, improving the pedagogical methodology of teaching dance art to young people, the student assumes the correct orientation of the students' specific interest and creativity in dance art.

Key words: choreography, national dance art, technology, classical music, tradition, creativity, folk music, pedagogical technologies.

Interest in the application of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, attention is gaining momentum day by day. One of the reasons for this is that, to this day, in traditional education, students-students are taught to master only their ready-made knowledge, while modern technologies teach them to search for the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and tax, correctly draw even Hatto conclusions themselves. It is up to them that the teacher and the student choose what technology to achieve the result from the goal, since the main goal of both parties is clear: the result is aimed

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at achieving, in which the student's level of Knowledge, Group character, technology used depending on the circumstances are selected, for example, to achieve the result, maybe video material. One of the requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short period of time, without excessive mental and physical exertion. The delivery of certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, their formation of skills and competencies in the field of certain activities, as well as control over the activities of students, assessment of the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by them requires a higher pedagogical skill from the teacher and a new approach to the educational process. I bring to your attention a small innovative technology that I have developed myself.

It is known that childhood is considered the best moments in the development of creative abilities from a psychological point of view. At this time, children become extremely curious, show a lot of fervor and great passion in the study of the universe. In this regard, parents attract them to various types of activities with the aim of satisfying their interests, increasing their childhood experience. And increasing knowledge and experience will provide a solid foundation for future creative activities. In addition, the mind of thinking children, the laws and rules that are hardened in the minds of adults, will be somewhat free and independent in relation to the limits imposed. It is desirable to develop comprehensively while these important aspects. Dance art creativity-glorifies a moral, spiritual life, that is, beauty, goodness and dignity, achieved in high maturity. Therefore, children can be raised spiritually mature through the art of dance and its examples, which are among the hereditary dances.

Increasing the creative activity of children is gradually developed on the basis of targeted education, expanding musical experience, gaining emotions, impressions, accelerating thoughts. At this age, emotions that arise from music listened to in children stimulate the birth of certain activity of movement in them. The educator's goal in this regard is seen in the fact that he finds a suitable and interesting musical - dance text, directing it to the right path. Moving towards music is a strict requirement imposed during the entire course of a child's dance routine. Movements should be based on music and reflect not only its general mood, but also clear means of expression.

Usually children's dances are generously accompanied by dance tunes and sung tunes. Children of school age (5-7 years old) should choose such actions when

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staging dances to the music itself, in which the typical simplicity, masculinity, sociability of children can be seen. Plot dances that reflect the interesting events they face in their lives are even more interesting and interesting to them when staged. A sense of patriotism is formed by staging a dance to songs from the motherland. Loyalty to the homeland in which they live, their family, neighborhood, loved ones, pride in what they have done and trying to fit them is explained. Through dances of similar content, creativity skills can be formed in young children. This is achieved by the educator through the use of techniques such as performing dance routines and elements, performing expressively, narrating the dance with an oral image, explaining it to them at the time of performance, reminding them. The use of the repetition exercise method is also of great importance. In children, not only to master the skills of movement, but also the skills of children to independently carry out creative tasks are formed. The content of the dance encourages them to think, think and verbally state the thoughts that arise in their minds. The circle of children's thinking expands. By performing actions, on the other hand, it is formed to increase the elegance of music for hearing and memorizing movements, to concentrate, to work physically. As a result, an increase in the creativity of children is achieved. The most important goal and task of music and dance education in young children is the formation of a truly musical and dance culture in them. In this, the main thing is to be able to analyze children's musical perception, musical taste, dance, develop their need and interests in dance. Shapes children's abilities to be able to listen to music and perform dance movements to the music.

In the dance lesson processes of children's schools of music and art, there is a special role of creativity in the development of students' creative abilities, mastering the exercises given in the subject of Uzbek dance, classical dance, folk stage dance. For this reason, in the course of the lesson for children, teachers will have to take into account some activities on the development of the creativity abilities of educators, as well as the organization of training during their work in cooperation with their students, and be well versed in children's psychology. Taking this into account and based on the results of our study, we considered it important to give the following recommendations:

Studying in the choreography department of children's schools of music and art is considered 5 years of education, depending on the development of creativity abilities of students in the course of the lesson as a long-term process, in its development, first of all, parents should help students to increase their interest in

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dancing and independently perform separate children's exercises in the family. Because it should remain the first task in the gal to properly establish the technical capabilities of students from the earliest age periods of physical education;

- Creativity development of abilities takes a lot of work and time. Therefore, it is appropriate to allow creativity to stimulate the individual during the development of abilities, and to take into account the desire and interests of the child. It is much easier to give him instructions if the child's interests and abilities correspond to the content of his activities, but on the contrary, in conditions where there is no interest and interest is not formed, creativity is the effort to develop the ability goes to;

- Creative work is considered a laborious activity due to the fact that it requires patience and endurance. Creativity the development of abilities also assumes the integrity and systematization of human life. This is due to the fact that creativity in children in the upbringing of the emotional volitional sphere for the formation and development of abilities, it is necessary to teach the child, the student to be persistent in working steadily on the tasks assigned to him, to feel his obligations, to go on assignments in a timely and consistent manner.

In conclusion, the introduction of the recommended work in this way into the educational process will be able to eliminate the problems that arise between baletmasters and teachers and students. At the next time in our country, the educational system has completely changed. In addition to education, the state has a wide focus on the field of art and culture. In particular, the president said, " let our country be a beautiful, beautiful, free and fair land. The words of Hope are important, " let our distant descendants remain a free and prosperous homeland." The work of carrying out these tasks is also associated with specialists engaged in the study and teaching of our Uzbek national dance art. The methods and techniques of improving Uzbek folk dance art and using innovative technologies in it are also widely promoted. The accumulation of scientific knowledge from year to year in the field of dance art is one of the most important branches of cultural studies on the basis of the scientific justification of the purpose, content and methods of Education. Practical experience in the modern educational system shows that a pre-carefully designed lesson will definitely give the teacher and student the opportunity to make the lesson interesting, as well as achieve a positive result, and increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

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